

Sustainability Disclosure on Environmental Reporting: A Review of Literature in Developing Countries

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Abstract: *In recent decades, environmental issues have emerged as a topic of increasing importance in the accounting literature. Environmental matters associated with industrial activities have increased public concerns about both financial and non-financial performance of firms leading to arising pressure for the disclosure and studies of environmental reporting, especially in developed countries. In the developing countries, however, relatively limited research in this area has been published, particularly in the Arab region. The main objective of this article is to present a review of recent literature on the sustainability accounting disclosure in developing countries. A number of theoretical frameworks have been developed to provide a further understanding of the concept of accounting for the disclosure. The literature reveals that the stakeholder theory is utilized in most studies. According to this theory, firms have to provide sustainability and environmental disclosure due to the pressures from all types of stakeholders and communities. Other theories which have been advanced to explain the disclosure practice include political economy, legitimacy, and institutional theory. In general, no specific theory is complete on its own or superior to another. The focus of this review is on identifying the determinants of the environmental disclosures and the current gap in those studies. These determinants can be divided into four groups. The first group examines the national contextual factors, the second group investigates the ownership structure, the third group evaluates companies' characteristics, and final group investigates governance attributes as the determinants of the environmental disclosure practice. The review reveals a large variation related to environmental disclosure level in developing countries. The article contributes to the literature by providing a further understanding of environmental disclosure practices in countries where published studies are still very limited. This study also provides recommendations and direction for future research on sustainability environmental disclosure*

Keywords: *Environmental reporting, Sustainability disclosure, Theoretical context, National contextual factors, and Developing Countries.*

1.0 Introduction

Nowadays, new regulations and requirements are main challenges which have forced most of the firms for preparing its environmental reporting. Furthermore, the potential of stakeholders and investors increased demand for disclosure and transparency on environmental activities in both mandatory and voluntary reporting which as resulting to improve firm's reputation and future prospects. Therefore, environmental issues regarding industrial activities have emerged public concerns about the non-financial performance and great pressure for the disclosure of environmental reporting, in order to assist the investors to evaluate the companies' performance in a better manner (Bhalla, 2018; Sekerez, 2017). The need of environmental protection legislation through the exercise of pressures on firms, in order to place more attention and dissemination of information about their environmental performance on their operating with social and environmental influence, because of raised awareness by internal and external stakeholders. In recent decades, there has been wide a spread opinion that firms, such as individuals and governments represent members of society that increase benefits from it, thus at the same time, they have a committing to "respond" the society in the same direction (ACCA, 2014; Haladu & Salim, 2016; Sahoo, Swain, & Bal, 2018).

Sustainability of environmental reporting is a substantial means of disclosure and transparency about organizations' policies and short- long-term strategies regarding the environmental activities to their stakeholders to provide evidence that they are responsible for their operation and the resulting effect on the environment (Chang, Oh, Park, & Jang, 2017; Oh, Chang, & Martynov, 2011; Perrault & Clark, 2016; Comyns,

2016). Thus, it is also evident that environmental reporting has become an essential aspect for firms to improve reputation and increasing competitive advantage (De Villiers, Naiker, & Van Staden, 2011; Lu, Abeysekera, & Cortese, 2015). Furthermore, in the recent decade De Villiers et al., (2011), mentioned two motives for improved environmental reporting and sustainability disclosure. First, firms are more probable to increase economic performance with disclosure on environmental activities. Second, to enhance corporations' internal and external legitimacy should be fulfilled and follow up with environmental laws and regulations by implementing recognized standards, such as and the International Organization for Standardization (ISO) guidelines and Global Reporting Initiative (GRI).

In spite of, it was recognized that developing countries awareness concerning environmental issues and attention on the environmental disclosure are still lower than in the developed world. Further, developing countries suffer from lack of stakeholder pressures and social expectations regarding the knowledge of environmental matters (K. Eljayash, 2017; K. M. Eljayash, 2015; Ismail & Rahman, 2016; Lu & Abeysekera, 2014; Mughal, 2014). Hence, disclosures of non-financial perspective will be higher through fulfillment by the long-term strategy and business vision and concentrate on future activities which would engage and create values for the different stakeholders including the society as well as the firm should recognize that it needs to properly convey information to promote connection with their stakeholders, and to look on as accountable towards environment issues (Lodhia, 2018; Mansor, Jamil, & Bahari, 2017).

The studies indicate that the most of prior literature interested with social and environmental disclosure have been held in the developed nations as well as, the firms in developed worlds are more attention paid to disclosure on its environmental accidents over the last four decades. Welbeck, Owusu, Bekoe, & Kusi, (2017) in a recent study investigated that environmental reporting has been deliberated broadly by many researchers and the accounting practice in developed countries have been improved in environmental disclosure and transparency over the years. Comparatively, a few evidence have been found on environmental reporting in developing countries (Aldrugi & Abdo, 2014; K. Eljayash, 2017; Yusoff, Othman, & Yatim, 2013).

Several researchers have concentrated on the factors that might have significant impact on environmental disclosure level to improve and enhancing transparency in its environmental reports, which would need to engage all types of stakeholders and also assist in increasing of companies' reputation (Amran, Zain, Sulaiman, Sarker, & Ooi, 2013; Bhalla, 2018). Furthermore, the majority of studies in environmental disclosure level and social accountability have applied theories to get a logical interpretation of disclosure behavior. There are many theories which have commonly been utilized to investigate and illuminate accounting issues regarding of environmental reporting practices such as legitimacy, stakeholder and institutional theories (Burgwal & Vieira, 2014; Van der Laan, 2009).

The main objective of this study seeks to review of recently published studies conducted in the developing countries in order to evaluate the theoretical context for these studies and take a look at the determinates or factors which have been influenced in sustainability disclosure of environmental reports, and then the study suggests some recommendations, as well as proposed for future studies, will be included in this section as well.

2.0 Literature Review

This section reviews the literature relating to sustainability disclosure on environmental reporting in developing countries and emerging nations. With regard to variables and determinants of sustainability disclosure in developing countries, most of the studies have converged widely the characteristics of companies as determinants of disclosure behavior towards environmental reporting rather than internal and external factors which may affect directly in the level of environmental disclosure. Thus the current study attempts to review the theoretical framework and factors which influenced environmental disclosure. To get a deeper understanding of these factors could be divided into four categories: The first category will examine the national contextual factors such as economic, political, the legal system and local culture. The second category will investigate the ownership structure of companies (e.g., foreign ownership, state ownership, institutional ownership, and

ownership concentration). The third category examines the companies' characteristics such as (nationality, industry type, size, and age of companies). The final category examines governance attributes as determinants of environmental disclosure level.

2.1 Types of disclosure used by companies

Through a review of literature, there are two types of disclosure namely mandatory and voluntary reports on the social and environmental impact of companies' activities, which have increasingly been published in the last years, are in most cases referred to as Corporate Sustainable Reports (CRS), though they can be found in a wide range of other terms. Hence, there was great pressure of international and national regulation and requirements, developed by national governments and international bodies, such as EU and UN, in the form of laws, instruction or guidelines to protect environment thus these new regulation imposing for preparing mandatory reports, instead of voluntary reports (Islam, 2017).

On the other hand, firms have a positive influence on the public perception of corporative image and reputation, so found they more often publish completely voluntary reports about their environmental activities and sustainability development. It is crucial to stress that voluntary nature of disclosure sustainability reports may lead to an incomplete picture of disclosure level on the impact of the company's activities. Therefore, in order to enable comparability and increase responsibility for the presented information, there are some researchers advocate the need for strongly regulation of the content of voluntary reports, with the purpose of enable comparability and increase accountability for providing actual information (Aldrugi & Abdo, 2014; Kuo & Yi-Ju Chen, 2013; Nickell & Roberts, 2014).

In this meaning, corporate sustainability reporting should point out how companies reduce or mitigate damaging environmental impact caused by their activities and what they plan to do about it in the next future. In the aspect of the better sharp of voluntary (non-mandatory) environmental reports of important utilize, are the efforts of many non-governmental and non-profit organizations, to suggest comprehensive frameworks for sustainability environmental reporting and require how firms should disclose numerous social and environmental issues. Among such organizations as broadly known are SRG (Sustainability Reporting Guidelines); GRI (Global Reporting Initiative) and International Organization for Standardization with a series of ISO standards (De Villiers et al., 2011; Sekerez, 2017; Uwuigbe, Egbide, & Ayokunle, 2011).

2.2 Choosing and justification for using theories

From theoretical literature reviews revealed many researchers are applied stakeholder theory to interpret the accounting issues related to environmental and social reporting practices of the corporation as a response to particular society or types of stakeholder because of their extremely pressure (Cooper & Owen, 2007; Jamali, 2008). There are others theories apart from this theory to emerge in the literature of social and environmental accounting which have also been adopted to interpret the issue regard to disclosure on environmental and social reports, that including the institutional theory and legitimacy theory (Amran & Keat Ooi, 2014; Omran & Ramdhony, 2015).

Using a theoretical framework can get a logical explanation related to incentives and motivations beyond practices of environmental and social reporting by firms. Prior studies of social and environmental accounting revealed applied that theories refers to firms activities in the advanced world and tend to engage more stakeholders to provide social and environmental information in annual reports (Deegan & Blomquist, 2006; Elijido-Ten, 2007; González-Benito & González-Benito, 2010). However, past studies indicate that business which ware adapted strategy about disclosure is avoided through a crisis of legitimacy, even though few could be presumed on the behavior of organizations activities in developing countries. For instance, the institutional theory and stakeholder theory are used in relation to providing more interpretation in environmental disclosure as well as the factors which have motivated behaviors' managerial in corporations. Companies which have operated in developing countries claim to the expectations and demands groups of stakeholder in terms of the

motivations behind providing information regarding environmental and social disclosure in annual reports (Azizul Islam & Deegan, 2008).

3.0 Review of theoretical approaches to environmental disclosure

From the published studies, it can be observed the majority of previous literature concerned with environmental reporting have been undertaken in Australia and many developed worlds. However, the Arabic regions have been suffering a general lack of knowledge and are still a relatively new practice on the accounting studies area related to environmental disclosure (K. Eljayash, 2017; Hewaidy, 2016). Though, not many studies have addressed environmental disclosure level in developing nations. Further, few published research have examined to provide new insights to determine environmental disclosure (quantity and quality) from the theoretical context of some theories. As a result, there is increasing demand and support for these theories to provide more for variances in the disclosure of environmental practice.

The study focusing on stakeholders' requirements and perceptions of corporate environmental disclosure has been conducted by Ahmad & Ishwerf, (2014) the study examined why firms make or do not make corporate environmental disclosure, and the theory applied in this study was the stakeholder theory to interpret the practices of environmental disclosure in Libyan firms. In addition, in Libya also study was investigated by Bayoud & Kavanagh, (2012), the extent of this research is the impact of environmental accountability disclosures on organizational performance, the study was used stakeholder theory, in order to provide an extremely support between environmental responsibility disclosures and organizational performance among companies in different sector. However, another study has been examined by Khlif, Guidara, & Souissi, (2015) indicated that information irregularity was decreased between executives and external users (such as investors) as a result of social and environmental information according to the economic theory approach. Based on the relationship between companies and social and environmental organizations according to the legitimacy and stakeholder theories, the study found the increase of environmental disclosure by firms to promote images and reputations and in turn for the legitimization of their societal existence.

Likewise, a new study conducted by Bhalla, (2018) tested the effect of company characteristics on environmental disclosure on the websites of the selected manufacturing companies listed on BSE for the financial years 2011-12 to 2015. The sample consists of 61 companies in different manufacturing industries. This study was supported the legitimacy theory as companies are to disclose about their social and environmental information because of their reputation. In contrast, in the study by Ezeagba, Rachael, & Chiamaka, (2017) they used only stockholder theory to interpret the association between environmental accounting disclosures and return on equity of food and beverage companies.

In the Middle East context, the study was investigated by Barakat, Pérez, & Ariza, (2015) compared between two countries to illustrate and evaluate disclosure of social responsibility including environmental reports. The study was used the institutional and legitimacy theories to explain the mechanisms of control used in organizations as a substitute for legal deficiencies according to the institutional theory. The study of Pakistani, according to Mahmood, Ahmad, Ali, & Ejaz, (2017) the study has been found the level of disclosure is increasing by good performers could be explained through the voluntary disclosure theory as an attempt to separate themselves from others, and bad performers increasing in the level of disclosure could be explained through legitimacy theory as an attempt to change the public perception. And aimed to understand whether patterns of environmental disclosure varies between the different categories (good, bad and mixed) of environmental performance. Also, another study conducted by Arshad, Muhammad, & Al Astal, (2015) two theories were applied in this study to examine financial crisis which occurred in 2008, in terms of social and environmental disclosure; namely, stakeholder and legitimacy theory.

Numerous theories review, it can be observed many research studies is used the stakeholder theory to explain the practices of environmental disclosure in companies as a result of increasing stockholders demands and high public pressures. From the published literature, other theories have been used to explain environmental

disclosure level, which include legitimacy, political economy theory and institutional theory. As widely known, it is not the specific theory is complete on its own or superior to another. Instead, it should be seen that the theories have similar theoretical backgrounds and provide combined and covering perspectives. From a theoretical perspective, the corporations, according to these theories, is part of a broader social system that could be influenced by numerous components. The study considers that these theories will provide insight into environmental reporting practices rather than adopting only one theory.

4.0 Review of the Factors Influencing Disclosure in Previous Literature

4.1 National contextual factors and environmental disclosure

Among several studies focusing on national factors which have been examined on environmental disclosure including (Bani-Khalid & Kouhy, 2017; K. M. Eljayash, 2015; Ibrahim, 2015; Nassr Saleh Mohamed Ahmad, 2004; Dong, Stettler, & Antonakis, 2007; De Villiers & Marques, 2016; Mohammed Bayoud, 2013; De Villiers & Marques, 2016; Williams, 1999; Adams, 2002).

According to Bani-Khalid & Kouhy, (2017), aimed to explore the views and perceptions of both internal and external stakeholders about the importance of the historical, political, economic, socio-cultural, and non-institutional factors in motivating the production of CSED information by Jordanian companies. By using semi-structured interviews; extracted information from multiple groups of stakeholders was divided into four main themes. The findings of this study provided that the political conditions, the legal system, cultural values, and economic development are all significant factors in explaining the level of CSER disclosure. Also, in the context of Jordan. The findings inducted that cultural factor seems to have the greatest impact on the corporate disclosure practices. An earlier study “document the environmental disclosure practices in the Arab Spring countries, Egypt, Libya, and Tunisia” has been conducted by (K. M. Eljayash, 2015). The sample size was 23 oil and gas companies in each of the countries, and content analysis and environmental disclosure index are used in this study. These revolutions have been influenced by political and legal systems, and economic development of these countries affected the accounting system, thus accounting practices, including environmental disclosure practices that be influenced.

Another study was conducted in Libya “investigated the internal and external factors which have been influenced on disclosure of environmental issues in the Libyan largest construction companies” by Ibrahim, (2015). Using content analysis of the annual reports and conducting semi-structured interviews and administration of the questionnaire was distributed. The results of the study revealed that the level of environmental disclosure among Libyan construction companies was very low. Similarly, the first study conducted in Libya by Ahmad, (2004) he examined the extent of practices of CED which were made by the all the largest industrial companies quoted on the Libyan industrial production administration for the years 1998-2001. Further, Ibrahim, (2015) provides the same conclusion as Ahmad, (2004) revealed the impact of the political, economic and social (external) factors reflects the indirect influence on the disclosure environment. In addition, it could be understood that the external environment for companies is considered to be a contextual determinant that may have a vital role to play in influencing the corporate activities of any country (Dong et al., 2007). Thus, organizations as socio-economic actors operate within the country structure, and also play a major role in promoting economic growth; they could consequently be affected by the existing political system of that country. In this context, a study conducted by (Mohammed Bayoud, 2013) he concluded that it is documented that the degree of political rights and civil liberties of any country may reflect the reality of corporate practices towards financial and non-financial disclosures in that country.

For example, it was found that firms with a higher level of democracy tend to disclose more information (De Villiers & Marques, 2016). In contrast, Williams, (1999) argued that a low level of corporate disclosure is linked largely with countries that have practiced civil oppression and violations of political rights. Besides that, national cultural values are reported as one of the external factors that determine the practices of social and environmental disclosures level. Adams, (2002) asserts that “there is an association between the cultural value context and corporate reporting,” which can assist to explain differences in the voluntary corporate disclosures.

4.2 Ownership Structure

Previous researches have mainly focused on the significant impact of ownership structure on social and environmental disclosure incentives. There are many current types of research on ownership structure and environmental disclosure in established developing countries including (Ahmed Haji, (2013); Alhazaimah, Palaniappan, & Almsafir, (2014); Sulaiman, Abdullah, & Fatima, (2014); Nurhayati, Taylor, & Tower, (2015); Ismail & Rahman, (2016); Alhazmi, (2017) ; Haladu & Salim, (2016); Alhazmi, (2017); Dintimala & Amril, (2018); Al_arussi & Al_dhamari, (2017); Akrouf & Othman, (2016); Haddad, AlShattarat, AbuGhazaleh, & Nobanee, (2015); Bani-Khalid & Kouhy, (2017).

A study was carried out in Malaysia by Ahmed Haji, (2013) examine corporate social responsibility (CSR) disclosures in the annual reports of 85 companies listed. The results of the study revealed that government ownership, director ownership have relationships with the extent and quality of CSR disclosures. Likewise, a study by Alhazaimah et al., (2014), the effects of board activity, foreign ownership, and block holder ownership on the voluntary disclosure in the annual reports of 72 listed companies in Jordan. Their findings reveal that foreign ownership, and block-holder ownership significant influencing the level of voluntary disclosure. In contrast, another study conducted in Malaysia by Sulaiman et al., (2014) on 164 annual reports of companies in the environmentally sensitive industries (ESI) provides evidence that share ownership had no significant relationship with the quality of environmental reporting. In the context of Indian, a study by Nurhayati et al., (2015) this study investigated the extent of social and environmental disclosure of textile firms, and the results suggest that the extent of voluntary disclosure is influenced by the ownership structure. The study also concludes that the levels of foreign ownership have a significantly positive impact on voluntary disclosure.

Similarity, earlier study was undertaken in developing countries by Ismail & Rahman, (2016) investigated the quality of environmental disclosure in different reporting mediums by 116 oil and gas firms. The finding of this study reveals the positive association between foreign ownership and quality of environmental disclosure. Moreover, in the context of Saudi Arabia, a study conducted on 169 companies by Alhazmi, (2017) the findings revealed that ownership structure has a significant influence on corporate social disclosure practices. Further, another recent study held in Malaysia corporate ownership and sustainability reporting: environmental agencies as moderating effects (Haladu & Salim, 2016). The sample size was 67 of Malaysia firms listed from 2009 to 2014. The outcome of this study showed that firm s' ownership has a significant relationship with environmental disclosure. Moreover, the presence of government ownership is likely to improve corporate environmental reporting practice. This finding was consistent with Al_arussi & Al_dhamari, (2017), also found that government ownership has a positive relationship with environmental disclosure. On the other hand, the association of ownership structure with the environmental disclosure of listed companies in the Middle Eastern and North African (MENA) emerging markets, has been investigated by Akrouf & Othman, (2016). The sample was collected from 347 annual reports. The finding showed that there is a negative association between family ownership and environmental disclosures. Further, the results indicate that number of shareholders and outside ownership are not related to voluntary disclosure base on a study of 57 non-financial Jordanian companies listed; this study was conducted by Haddad et al., (2015).

A sample size of 150 listed firms of Indonesian on proper Stock Exchange (BSE) from 2010 to 2014 was studied by Dintimala & Amril, (2018). The findings of this study inducted that all ownership structure were lower, the firms published reports related to environmental disclosure, when total assets higher, firms with higher environmental compliance according to proper firms in manufacturing and mining sectors of oil and gas (PEM), and the score of environmental performance higher. The results were consistent with all hypotheses. However, the study stated by Bani-Khalid & Kouhy, (2017), showed that ownership structure is not related to the disclosure practice.

4.3 Company characteristics

Firm characteristics are one of the common factors that have been examined within different contexts of developing countries. In environmental disclosure context, many previous studies have investigated the

relationship between several dimensions of disclosure and different company characteristics including (Kabra, 2015; Aldrugi & Abdo, 2014; Bayoud & Kavanagh, 2012; Nawaiseh, 2015; Ezhilarasi & Kabra, 2017; Innocent & Gloria, 2018; Bani-Khalid & Kouhy, 2017; Nguyen, Tran, Nguyen, & Le, 2017).

A recent study showed by Kabra, (2015) examined the influence of selected company variables on environmental disclosures practices. 2009-10 to 2013-14 was the period used for this study. Content analysis was used to analyze the data; the result revealed the company size, company age, and environmental certification are important factors in explaining environmental disclosures practices. Two studies have investigated in Libya by (Aldrugi & Abdo, 2014; Bayoud & Kavanagh, 2012). The sample size was 40 of the companies industry and their results inducted that there is a positive relationship between company size, age, industry type and the levels of social and environmental disclosure. However, Nawaiseh, (2015) provides evidence that the company size has is a negative relationship with social disclosure.

Also, another study of using a sample size of 50 firms from 2007 to 2011 in Egypt has been examined by (Ezhilarasi & Kabra, 2017). This study utilized content analysis, and the results of this study stated the factors of firms' characteristics such as (firm size and firm financial leverage) have an insignificant relationship with environmental information disclosure as well as firm's profitability showed positively on the other hand firm's age had a significant negative relationship with EID. Another evidence by Innocent & Gloria, (2018) they also report that firm size, profitability, and firm age have a significant and positive effect on environmental performance.

In the context of Jordan, research was conducted by Bani-Khalid & Kouhy, (2017) examined how corporate characteristics could influence the amount of Corporate Social and Environmental Disclosure (CSED) in the manufacturing sector. The results indicated that the firm size, type of audit firm are significantly associated with the amount of CSED. On the other hand, find that firm profitability, age, type of industry and ownership are not related to the practices of CSED. In contrast, a new study assessing factors affecting disclosure levels of environmental accounting information has been tested by Nguyen, Tran, Nguyen, & Le, (2017). The sample was collected from 74 construction firms listed on the Vietnam Stock Exchange for the period from 2013 to 2016. The results pointed out that the level of disclosure is influenced by factors of firm size, profitability, and financial leverage.

4.4 Governance attributes

Many prior studies provided evidence about the influence of governance attributes on the level of environmental disclosure practices in developing nations (e.g. Grace & Ndubuisi, 2018; Alhazmi, 2017; Samaha, Khelif, & Hussainey, 2015; Rouf, 2011; Rafique, Malik, Waheed, & Khan, 2017; Ezhilarasi & Kabra, 2017; Masud, Nurunnabi, & Bae, 2018; Nandi & Ghosh, 2013; Masud et al., 2018; Das, 2014; Dibia & Onwuchekwa, 2015).

In Africa context, a study has been done by Grace & Ndubuisi, (2018) aimed to compare the impact of corporate board characteristics on the extent of environmental disclosure quantity of listed firms in two leading emerging economies in Africa, South Africa, and Nigeria. The sample was comprised of 303 firms including environmentally sensitive companies purposively selected for content analysis study in South Africa (213) and Nigeria (90). The results reveal a more significant positive association between board characteristics and environmental disclosure in South Africa and less relevant association in Nigeria. Under the same category of governance attributes Alhazmi, (2017) emphasizes on factors such as board size and board meeting frequency and based on this study the attributes have such a significant relationship with social disclosure.

The board size, board composition, audit committee have a significant positive with voluntary disclosure was also studied by Samaha et al., (2015). The sample of this study was of 64 listed companies of developed and developing countries, and content analysis was the disclosure index. The results board size, board composition, and the audit committee have a significant positive effect on voluntary disclosure. The same conclusion was reported by Rouf, (2011) he found the board size, board leadership structure and board audit committee have a positive association with voluntary disclosure.

Several studies discuss a positive effect on board size on the level of environmental disclosure among listed firms. For example, in Pakistan, the board has a positive correlation with environmental reporting (Rafique et al., 2017) and other researches (Nandi & Ghosh, 2013) also investigate the relationship between firm characteristics, corporate governance attributes and the level of corporate disclosure of listed firms in India. The same results suggest a positive relationship between board size, the ratio of audit committee members to total board members, family control, CEO duality, firm size, profitability, liquidity and the extent of corporate disclosure.

In addition, a recent study by Masud et al., (2018) investigated the influence of corporate governance mechanism on environmental reporting in South Asian countries. The study compared between three Asian countries (India, Bangladesh, and Pakistan), and 88 listed organizations' sustainability reports during the years 2009–2016 from the Global Reporting Initiative (GRI) database. Their empirical findings indicate the foreign and institutional ownership, board independence, and board size have a positive association with environmental reporting. With a similar conclusion was reported by Masud et al., (2018) they also found that foreign institutional ownership is the most important corporate governance attribute that engages corporates in environmental disclosure behavior. By used content analysis of annual reports for a sample of 177 most polluting companies in India.

However, in the Bangladesh context, a study has been found by Das, (2014) examines the potential factors of corporate governance characteristics, firm characteristics and ownership structure on voluntary environmental reporting. A sample of the study consists of 123 companies with 861 firm-year observations listed in the Dhaka Stock Exchange. His finding emphasis that audit committee and board size have a non-significant relationship with voluntary environmental reporting. No different results were stated (Dibia & Onwuchekwa, 2015) investigated the sample of 15 companies drawn from the oil and gas sectors of the Nigerian stock exchange. They also found that there is no significant association between the type of audit firm and the level of environmental disclosure.

5.0 Conclusion, Recommendation and Future Research

The literature on environmental reporting is very rich and addresses an extensive variety of sustainability disclosure related issues. Generally, the main aim of this study has been to review the theoretical framework and factors that impact the disclosure of environmental reporting in developing countries. Through a review of the theoretical framework has revealed that several of the researchers have applied many theories in order to get a further interpretation of the issue related to environmental disclosure. Furthermore, from prior literature, it can be observed the stakeholder theory is used in most studies to interpret the disclosure of environmental reporting practices in firms, due to the pressure from all types of stakeholders and communities as a whole. From the review of environmental accounting, literature has other theories used to illuminate sustainability reporting on environmental disclosure practices, namely, political economy, legitimacy, and institutional theory. Further, Cotter, Lokman, & Najah, (2011) define that six theories have been used commonly to interpret the factors of the disclosure in environmental accounting, namely, agency theory, signaling theory, the theory of proprietary cost, political economy theory, stakeholder theory, and legitimacy theory. In general, no specific theory is complete on its own or superior to another.

Thus, most of the studies have mentioned that the disclosure level in firms of advanced nations has placed much greater concern to environmental reporting studies over the past four decades (Mbekomize & Wally-Dima, 2013). However, developing countries in general and Arabic nations, in particular, has been suffering a general lack of knowledge in the accounting issue regard to environmental disclosure aspects (K. Eljayash, 2017; Hewaidy, 2016). With regarding to variables and factors of environmental disclosure in developing countries, numerous of studies have focused on the characteristics of companies as determinants of disclosure on environmental reporting (e.g. Bani-Khalid & Kouhy, 2017; Innocent & Gloria, n.d.; Kabra, 2015), rather than national factors such as (economic, political, legal system and firms culture), which have been effected in the level of environmental disclosure.

As a result, a complete picture of the relationship between the characteristics of companies and the level of environmental disclosure has not yet provided by prior studies. Evidence that the findings which have been obtained from previous studies were mostly different even in the same country regarding the effects of the factors examined on the disclosure levels. Moreover, a minority of these studies focused on the level of the disclosure contained in the reports with less attention paid to the quality of environmental disclosure. Furthermore, the emphasis is on annual reports to examine environmental disclosure, while other disclosure media have been ignored. In addition, a few studies have investigated the combined factors affecting environmental disclosure only of the three groups (e.g., national contextual factors, ownership structure, and company characteristics) in a single study.

6.0 Recommendation

According to, the previous research findings, this study can recommend that there were variances in results obtained regarding the effects of factors examined on the disclosure levels. Further, developing countries which have suffered from a lack of research in this field, thus need more research should be conducted to address the gaps in research and the inclusiveness of studies on environmental disclosure. Besides, the role Non-Government Organization (NGOs) and media as a pressure group supporting for improving the level of awareness of the public and encourage firms to disclose on environmental reporting in Arabic countries have been absented.

Most developing countries are not follow-up and fulfill with regulations and environmental laws by implementing recognized standards, such as the ISO 26000 and Global Reporting Initiative (GRI). Thus, this research recommends for a more proactive effort from standard-setting bodies on the need to adopt a standard and guideline for the mandatory disclosure of environmental reporting.

From a review of published studies undertaken in developing countries. New research might extend the scope of this study by involving comparative studies between developing and developed countries. Moreover, the study is needed to shed light on the role of specific factors in influencing the sustainability disclosure on environmental reporting practices such as accounting education, the power of non-government organization and modern media like websites (corporate homepage) and social networks as well as reports that are published by other languages could be included in future research.

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